

Chaucer on Transfinite Cardinals

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1 Introduction

Lo, 'tis the Cardinal Flow Exponentials,
Ethereal treasures in mathematical shells.
As we contemplate this flow of math,
Pondering on the many paths.
Let $\bigcup_{i=0}^{2^N} \circ 3(n+i)^3$ be the sum,
Of numbers and their powers, to the max they come.
And for $[\bigcup_b^a g(q) \int_1^N dB] \in [N]_i^i, C^x$,
We find the bound $\aleph_0$, an infinite hex.
And let us not forget the letter f and g ,
Functions, their inputs a mighty beg.
The sum $\bigcup_{r=0}^a \prod_{\Phi \in p} e_r \sigma_f \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \delta \omega_{0-m}^r \sqcup \mathbf{I}_{\omega, \alpha} = 1$,
With its many components, a puzzle unsolved, yet fun.
For M_n , a mirror construction dark,
We find $\aleph_{l_{ii}}^k(M) = \aleph | \bigcap_{i=1}^{\aleph(f_\gamma)} \aleph_{\pm} \aleph_{l_{ii}}^k(M_{ii_1}), \aleph_{\pm} \aleph_{l_{ii}}^k(M_{\nu i_{jj}})$, a complex mark.
And in S_n , a sigma adic sum,
We observe $\aleph_{l_{ii}}^k(S_n) \neq \aleph | \bigcap_{i=1}^{\aleph(f_\gamma)} \aleph_{l_{ii}}(S_{n, x_1})$, a peculiar num.
And in B_n , a binary sigma adic form,
We see $\aleph_{l_{ii}}^k(B_n) \equiv \aleph | \prod_{i=1}^{\aleph_k} \alpha n_i(\alpha)$, a grandiose norm.
Intriguing these concepts, imbedded in math,
Mysteries of the cardinal flow, in symbiotic path.
in other words,
Behold, the cardinal flow exponentials, A union of two to the power of N,
Brought together by the circle operator, And multiplied by three times n plus
i, squared and cubed.
Let us also consider a set, An open union from a to b, With a function g of
the integral, From 1 to N, raised to the power of i minus 1, Multiplied by dB,
all within the set of N, to the power of i, to the power of i, with the help of C
to the power of x.
Next, we have a special set, A closed intersection of different indices, With
a vector of E, indexed by r-1, Multiplied by F to the power of i-1, And equal to
the vector of E with index t, Times the sum of z sub r, from 0 to k-1, Multiplied

by $1 - R_{zr}$, with indices i and z sub r , all within the intersection, Which we define as aleph one.

Finally, let us consider two functions, f and g , With a unique input, a union of a to r , Multiplied by a product of ϵ , And some complex terms represented by σ , δ , and ω , All raised to various powers, Multiplied by the intersection of ω and α , And then summed to equal one.

Onward to the symbols of mirrors and sums, For a matrix $M_{n \times n}$, operating as a mirror, Then the cardinality of the intersection with its double subscript, Is equal to the cardinality of the intersection, Of say f_{γ} times the cardinality of M_{i_1} , *AlongwiththecardinalityofMsubnvisubjj*.

But should we consider the sigma sum $S_{n \times n}$, Then the cardinality of its intersection, Is not equal to the cardinality, Of say f_{γ} times the cardinality of $S_{n \times n}$, with its subscript $x_{1 \times 1}$.

And finally, for a binary sigma truncated sum, $B_{n \times n}$, The cardinality of its intersection, Will be the same as the product, Of all possible $\alpha_{n \times i}$ of α .